

Photooxidation of substituted pyrimidines in presence of peroxydisulphate in aqueous solution

M. Sudha Swaraga, L. Charitha and M. Adinarayana*

Department of Chemistry, Osmania University, Hyderabad-500 007, India

E-mail : mundra_adinarayana@hotmail.com

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Photooxidation of pyrimidine bases viz. thymine, uracil, cytosine, 5-bromouracil and 6-methyluracil in presence of peroxydisulphate (PDS) in aqueous solution at natural pH (7.5) has been carried out in a quantum yield reactor using a high-pressure mercury lamp. The reaction between pyrimidine and $\text{SO}_4^{\bullet-}$ is followed by measuring the absorbance of pyrimidine at its λ_{max} . The rate of oxidation of pyrimidine is calculated from the plot of absorbance vs time using microcal origin computer program on a personal computer. On the basis of these experimental results and product analysis a probable mechanism has been suggested in which peroxydisulphate ion on photolysis gives sulphate radical anions which initiates the reactions by adding to C(5) or C(6) position of pyrimidine base leading to the formation of pyrimidine base radical via radical cation or hydrolysis. The pyrimidine radical further reacts with PDS to give the final products.

When DNA is subjected to ionizing radiation many different changes can occur ranging from various kinds of base modifications to single and double strand breaks¹. Even though sugar radicals are actually responsible for strand break formation in DNA, experimental results clearly indicate that base radicals can contribute significantly via transfer of radical sites from base moiety to sugar moiety². Strand breaks are considered to be a very serious kind of damage to DNA^{2,3}.

Ionizing radiation causes damage to DNA by direct effect and indirect effect. The former is caused by the absorption of the ionizing radiation by the DNA molecule itself, the later by water radicals generated upon absorption of the ionizing radiation by water. It is very difficult to distinguish experimentally between these two modes of damage formation in DNA. On the absorption of ionizing radiation, DNA molecule undergoes a chemical change giving radical cation which on spontaneous deprotonation gives DNA radical, the chemistry of which is similar to DNA radicals produced by OH radicals. A key process of the direct effect is

The reactions of water derived radicals with DNA and its components have been extensively studied in dilute solutions. In contrast, our knowledge concerning the direct effect is very limited chiefly for reasons of practical nature.

In the direction of understanding the nature of direct effect of radiation on DNA, a method to mimic the direct effect by chemical means using $\text{SO}_4^{\bullet-}$ radicals has been adopted. The $\text{SO}_4^{\bullet-}$ radicals are generated *in situ* by the photolysis of peroxydisulphate. The kinetics of the reaction of $\text{SO}_4^{\bullet-}$ with several substituted pyrimidines have been carried out to understand the mechanism of oxidation and presented in the present communication.

Results and discussion

Photooxidation of pyrimidines have been carried out in aqueous solution in presence of peroxydisulphate. The rates of oxidation of pyrimidines have been measured under different experimental conditions. An increase in [pyrimidine] at constant [PDS] and constant light intensity has no effect on the rate of oxidation of pyrimidine (Table 1). At constant [pyrimidine] and light intensity increase in [PDS] has been found to increase the rate of oxidation (Table 1). Increase in light intensity has been found to increase the rate of oxidation at constant [PDS] and [pyrimidine] (Table 2). The quantum yield of oxidation of pyrimidines have been found to depend on [pyrimidine] and light intensity and independent of [PDS] (Tables 3 and 4). The irradiated aqueous solutions of pyrimidine and PDS has been analysed in HPLC using UV-visible detector. In the oxidation of thymine by $\text{SO}_4^{\bullet-}$ two peaks were observed with retention times 10.3 and 3.2 min in which 10.3 min corresponds to thymine and the other at 3.2 min corresponds to 5,6-dihydroxythymine which was further confirmed by authentic sample (Fig.1).

Table 1. Effect of [PDS] and [substrate] on rate of oxidation of pyrimidines by sulphate radical anion ($\text{SO}_4^{\bullet-}$) in aqueous solutionLight intensity = 2.16×10^{15} quanta s^{-1} , pH = 7.5, temp. = 300 K

Sl. no.	$10^4 \times [\text{PDS}]$ (mol dm^{-3})	$10^5 \times [\text{substrate}]$ (mol dm^{-3})	$10^7 \times \text{rate/mol dm}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$				
			Thymine	Uracil	Cytosine	5-Bromouracil	6-Methyluracil
1.	8.000	5.000	1.50	7.60	3.72	0.617	2.51
2.	6.000	5.000	1.13	5.80	2.70	0.494	2.00
3.	4.000	5.000	0.760	4.00	1.86	0.324	1.27
4.	2.000	5.000	0.380	2.00	0.930	0.197	0.662
5.	1.000	5.000	0.200	1.00	0.520	0.120	0.310
6.	1.000	2.000	0.190	1.00	0.524	0.110	0.325
7.	1.000	1.000	0.190	1.00	0.490	0.101	0.355

Table 2. Effect of light intensity on the rate of oxidation of pyrimidines by sulphate radical anion ($\text{SO}_4^{\bullet-}$) in aqueous solution[PDS] = 5.00×10^{-4} mol dm^{-3} , [Pyrimidine] = 5.00×10^{-5} mol dm^{-3} , temp. = 300 K, pH = 7.5

Sl. no.	$10^{15} \times \text{Intensity of light}$ (quanta s^{-1})	$10^7 \times \text{rate/mol dm}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$				
		Thymine	Uracil	Cytosine	5-Bromouracil	6-Methyluracil
1.	2.16	0.986	4.80	2.20	0.418	1.43
2.	2.55	1.36	6.00	4.01	0.587	2.17
3.	3.14	1.76	7.65	6.10	0.790	2.70

Table 3. Effect of [PDS] and [substrate] on quantum yields of oxidation of pyrimidines by sulphate radical anion ($\text{SO}_4^{\bullet-}$) in aqueous solutionLight intensity = 2.16×10^{15} quanta s^{-1} , pH = 7.5, temp. = 300 K

Sl. no.	$10^4 \times [\text{PDS}]$ (mol dm^{-3})	$10^5 \times [\text{substrate}]$ (mol dm^{-3})	ϕ				
			Thymine	Uracil	Cytosine	5-Bromouracil	6-Methyluracil
1.	8.000	5.000	2.14	13.3	4.07	0.494	3.01
2.	6.000	5.000	2.12	13.3	3.86	0.502	3.60
3.	4.000	5.000	2.11	13.6	3.91	0.481	3.41
4.	2.000	5.000	2.07	13.5	3.85	0.570	3.46
5.	1.000	5.000	2.16	13.4	4.28	0.638	3.20
6.	1.000	2.000	0.820	6.00	1.74	0.248	1.36
7.	1.000	1.000	0.425	2.78	0.830	0.122	0.756

Table 4. Effect of light intensity on the quantum yields of oxidation of pyrimidines by sulphate radical anion ($\text{SO}_4^{\bullet-}$) in aqueous solution[PDS] = 5.00×10^{-4} mol dm^{-3} , [Pyrimidine] = 5.00×10^{-5} mol dm^{-3} , temp. = 300 K, pH = 7.5

Sl. no.	$10^{15} \times \text{Intensity of light}$ (quanta s^{-1})	ϕ				
		Thymine	Uracil	Cytosine	5-Bromouracil	6-Methyluracil
1.	2.16	2.20	13.3	3.74	0.503	3.04
2.	2.55	2.62	13.8	5.75	0.600	3.70
3.	3.14	2.70	14.5	7.11	0.655	4.02

In the oxidation of uracil by $\text{SO}_4^{\bullet-}$ three peaks were observed with retention times 4.9, 4.1 and 3.2 min and in which 4.9 min corresponds to uracil and the other at 4.1 min corresponds to isobarbituric acid and 3.2 min corresponds to 5,6-dihydroxyuracil which was further confirmed by authentic samples. In the oxidation of cytosine by $\text{SO}_4^{\bullet-}$ three peaks were observed with retention times 4.1, 3.8 and 3.2 min and in which 3.8 min corresponds to cytosine and the other at 4.1 min corresponds to isobarbituric acid and 3.2 min corresponds to 5,6-dihydroxyuracil which was further

confirmed by authentic sample. It has been reported⁴ that OH radicals preferentially add to the C5/C6 double bond on reaction with uracil and substituted uracils leading to C5-OH and/or C6-OH adduct radicals. The radicals formed by attachment to C6 have oxidizing properties with respect to *N,N,N',N'*-tetramethyl-*p*-phenylenediamine (TMPD); those produced by addition to C5 are able to reduce tetranitromethane (TNM⁵). These differences in redox properties have been utilised to determine OH attachment between C5 and C6. The OH radical addition has been found to be at C5 for 1,3-dimethyluracil and 1,3,6-trimethyluracil while it is

at C6 for thymine. This difference in reactivity has been attributed to steric hindrance of methyl group at C5 position in thymine⁶⁻⁸. It is also reported that C5-OH adduct radicals are further oxidized to substituted isobarbituric acid as the main product while C6-OH adduct radicals in thymine are oxidized to 5,6-dihydroxythymine. With uracil, thymine and cytosine OH addition takes place predominantly at C5 to give 6-yl radicals which have reducing properties due to α substitution of the carbon centered 6-yl radical by nitrogen. The increase in rate of oxidation of 6-methyluracil by $\text{SO}_4^{\bullet-}$ observed in the present work compared to thymine (5-methyluracil) (Table 1) indicates that $\text{SO}_4^{\bullet-}$ might be predominantly attacking at C(5) position of pyrimidine leading to C(6)-yl radical. The positive inductive effect of methyl group at C(6)-position of 6-methyluracil increases the reducing nature of C(6)-yl radical and hence the rate of oxidation. The decrease in rate for 5-bromouracil compared with thymine (Table 1) shows that Br being bulkier than methyl group offers more steric hindrance. In view of the above discussions and experimental results, the scheme of photooxidation taking uracil as an example could be written as follows :

The sulphate radical anion ($\text{SO}_4^{\bullet-}$), produced by the photolysis of peroxydisulphate in the initiation step, is isostructural and isoelectronic with phosphate radical anion ($\text{PO}_4^{\bullet-}$), and therefore is expected to react in a similar fashion. Thus in our present study it is proposed that $\text{SO}_4^{\bullet-}$ reacts with pyrimidine bases at the C(5)/C(6) double bond. The marginal influence of light intensity on quantum yield suggests the role of light is mainly restricted to the generation of $\text{SO}_4^{\bullet-}$ from PDS in the initiation step. Since oxidation of pyrimidines is not observed in the absence of PDS on shining light, the increase in quantum yield with increase in [pyrimidine] suggests that the excited pyrimidine might be acting as a sensitizer to transfer its energy to PDS. The fact that the reaction rates are independent of [pyrimidine] suggests that sulphate radical anion reacts with pyrimidine in a fast step. The increase in reaction rate with increase in [PDS] suggests that PDS might react with C(5)-OH or C(6)-OH radicals to give final products. The quantum

yields of the reaction are greater than one indicating that $\text{SO}_4^{\bullet-}$ might be propagating a chain reaction.

It is reported⁹⁻¹¹ that OH radicals add to uracil, thymine and cytosine predominantly at C(5) to give C(6)-yl radical which have reducing properties due to the α -substitution of the carbon centered 6-yl radical by nitrogen. The increase in rate of oxidation of 6-methyluracil by $\text{SO}_4^{\bullet-}$ observed in the present work compared to thymine (5-methyluracil) (Table 1) indicates that $\text{SO}_4^{\bullet-}$ might be predominantly attacking at C(5) position of pyrimidine leading to C(6)-yl radical. The positive inductive effect of methyl group at C(6)-position of 6-methyluracil increases the reducing nature of C(6)-yl radical and hence the rate of oxidation. The decrease in rate for 5-bromouracil compared with thymine (Table 1) shows that Br being bulkier than methyl group offers more steric hindrance. In view of the above discussions and experimental results, the scheme of photooxidation taking uracil as an example could be written as follows :

Experimental

Pyrimidine bases viz. uracil, cytosine, thymine, 5-bromouracil, 6-methyluracil and PDS solutions were prepared using a double distilled water. Irradiations were carried out

Fig. 1. The optical chromatogram at 220 nm of photooxidation of thymine in presence of peroxydisulphate. Retention times 3.2 and 10.3 min correspond to product of thymine, 5,6-dihydroxythymine and unreacted thymine.

in a quantum yield reactor, QYR-20 using high pressure mercury lamp. The intensity at 254 nm is measured taking peroxydisulphate chemical actinometry as standard⁴. In a typical reaction, uracil or substituted uracil and PDS solutions are taken in a specially designed 1 cm path length cuvette, which is suitable, both for irradiation in the reactor as well as absorbance measurements. The irradiations were interrupted at regular intervals of time and the absorbance measurements are carried out on Hitachi UV-Visible spectrophotometer 3410. The progress of the reactions are monitored by measuring the absorbance at the respective λ_{\max} of pyrimidines. The reaction rates with respect to pyrimidines have been calculated from the plots of absorbance vs time using a computer program. A representative spectra is shown in Fig. 2. The quantum yields of the reactions have been calculated from the rates of oxidation of pyrimidine and calculated light intensity absorbed by PDS at 254 nm. This is the wavelength at which peroxydisulphate is activated to radical reactions. The light intensity absorbed by PDS was calculated using the following equation.

$$I_{\text{PDS}} = \frac{\epsilon_{\text{PDS}}[\text{PDS}]}{\epsilon_{\text{PDS}}[\text{PDS}] + \epsilon_{\text{Pyrimidine}}[\text{pyrimidine}]} \times I_t \quad (1)$$

I_{PDS} = The intensity of light absorbed by peroxydisulphate in the reaction mixture, I_t = total intensity of light measured from peroxydisulphate actinometry, ϵ_{PDS} = the molar absorption coefficient of peroxydisulphate at 254 nm, ($24.1 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and $\epsilon_{\text{pyrimidine}}$ = the molar absorption coef-

Fig. 2. Absorption spectra of photooxidation of thymine in presence of peroxydisulphate at different irradiation times. [Thymine] = $5.00 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, [PDS] = $4.00 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, Light intensity = $2.16 \times 10^{15} \text{ quanta s}^{-1}$: (1) 0, (2) 1, (3) 3, (4) 8 min.

ficient of pyrimidines viz. thymine, uracil, cytosine, 5-bromouracil and 6-methyluracil at 254 nm ($6200, 7700, 4500, 5900$ and $3220 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$).

The HPLC system used for analysis of products includes Shimadzu LC-10AT equipment with a dual piston-pump system, a solvent programmer and a Reodhyne injector 7725 fitted with 20 μl loop. A prepacked octadecylsilyl silica gel ODS hypersil column 25 cm \times 0.46 cm, mean particle size 5 μm was used. The column effluents were monitored at 220 nm, using variable wavelength SPD-10A UV-visible detector equipped with an 8 μl flow cell. Samples were eluted with aqueous solutions containing 5% (v/v) methanol and buffered with 10 mM KH_2PO_4 solution adjusted to pH 7.0. Before use the phosphate buffer was filtered through a millipore type HA 0.45 μm membrane filter. All mobile phases were degassed using a vacuum pump. The solvent flow rate was kept constant at 1.0 ml/min and all the HPLC runs were carried out at ambient temperature.

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